

Rac-5c

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-187-rac-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1
Vial:	31	Acq. Method Set:	30%quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 187 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/24/2021 5:09:05 PM CST		
Date Processed:	11/24/2021 6:31:45 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.256	10354501	50.05	652372
2	11.285	10333279	49.95	454685

Asy-5c

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-4-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1
Vial:	89	Acq. Method Set:	30%quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 4
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/24/2021 2:31:14 PM CST		
Date Processed:	11/24/2021 5:21:10 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.511	12457912	97.62	736625
2	11.753	303624	2.38	13085